

The dark cloud: Data centers as a new frontline for the climate movement

Discussion paper

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About the series

This is part of a series of discussion papers exploring strategic directions for the climate movement. Previous papers have examined [extreme weather events as organising opportunities](#) and [strategic adaptation](#). This paper, co-authored by Philip Eubanks (Executive Director of [Climate Emergency Fund](#), Saul Levin (Program Director at the [Center for Nonviolent Conflict Research](#)) and Cathy Rogers (Director of Research and Development at [Social Change Lab](#)) explores the rapid global expansion of data centers - driven largely by the artificial intelligence boom - and look at how it might represent one of the most promising organising opportunities the climate movement has seen in years.

Keywords: data centers; artificial intelligence; climate movement; community resistance; democratic accountability

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A movement is already well underway

On 31 March 2026, the Virginia Court of Appeals issued a [unanimous ruling](#) that effectively halted the Digital Gateway project - a proposed complex of 37 data centers and 14 substations spanning 22 million square feet, adjacent to the [Manassas National Battlefield Park](#). The coalition that fought it is a textbook case of cross-partisan organising: a 254-member suburban homeowners' association, the American Battlefield Trust, the National Parks Conservation Association, and local environmental groups, united in opposition to what the Coalition to Protect Prince William County called "everything that is broken with the data center industry - from the distortion of good local governance, to the complete abdication of oversight on an industry that is taking too much... power, water, and land."

In the November 2024 elections that preceded the ruling, every remaining Town Council member who had backed the project lost their seat.

The Digital Gateway project is not an isolated case. Between May 2024 and March 2025, an estimated [\\$64 billion in US data center projects were blocked or delayed](#). Communities in at least 14 states have enacted temporary moratoriums on new construction. In Michigan alone, at least [19 communities have proposed or implemented moratoria](#). In December 2025, Senator Bernie Sanders became the first member of Congress to call for a national pause on data centers; along with Rep, Ocasio-Cortez, the [AI Data Center Moratorium Act](#) has now been introduced. Monterey Park in California is [well on the way](#) to outright banning data centers in the city and Maine looked set to become the [first state to push pause](#) on data center build out before a bill that went through both chambers was vetoed by Governor Janet Mills. The moratorium movement has leapt from local town boards to state legislatures and into a national debate.

This is happening at extraordinary speed and it is frequently bipartisan. Heritage preservationists and property-rights conservatives have found themselves working alongside environmentalists and digital rights campaigners. Rural communities defending agricultural land are finding common cause with urban residents worried about water and energy costs. As one [Wall Street Journal](#) commenter put it: "Doubling your electric bill so that companies can figure out how to eliminate your job doesn't sound like a big winning proposition."

For the climate movement, this emerging organic resistance represents a rare strategic opportunity. While carbon reduction targets can feel remote and intangible, data centers,

right there in residential areas, are the opposite. They are a physical manifestation of big tech consolidation, and extractive capitalism, which bring with them higher utility bills and threats to natural ecosystems. They can bring together disparate concerns and grievances and focus them sharply on one big ugly building.

What are the grievances?

The grievances driving this movement are remarkably similar across the political spectrum, even if the emphasis varies by community. Water consumption figures, electricity cost projections and land use claims vary enormously by location and are sometimes disputed (for examples of these disputes, see [Construction Physics on water](#), [Harvard Law School on electricity costs](#), and [American Farm Bureau on land](#)). But movements are built on the harms that feel most immediate and controllable, and they point toward a deeper concern that decisions with sweeping consequences are being made without public consent.

Rising electricity bills are the single most politically potent issue - and perhaps the one that unites left and right most powerfully. A [recent analysis](#) of the latest [International Energy Agency](#) numbers found that 5% of the US's electricity is used for data centers. This is very unevenly spread; in some states, data centers make up more than 10% of demand and even higher. In Virginia, [estimates are that 25% of electricity consumption](#) was for data centers and a [JLARC independent study](#) projected that residents could be paying up to \$37 more per month by 2040. In Indiana, residential utility bills [rose 17.5 per cent in a single year](#), prompting Republican Governor Mike Braun to declare "we can't take it anymore." In Georgia, [monthly electricity bills have risen six times in two years](#), now averaging \$175 a month. As the founder of consumer group PowerLines [told Fortune](#), electricity prices are becoming "the new eggs". The scale of the build-out is huge. The [International Energy Agency](#) estimates that by 2030, data center energy demand could exceed the total electricity consumption of Japan. A [Global Action Plan UK](#) report estimated that a 2.7 million tonne increase in annual UK emissions from data centers would effectively wipe out the carbon savings expected from the switch to electric cars.

Water consumption runs a close second - the number one concern cited in press accounts of contested projects. In Tucson, Arizona, a proposal codenamed "Project Blue" would have diverted millions of gallons of drinking water from the desert for cooling and initially [the city council voted unanimously to reject it](#) after sustained public opposition. [Research by Shaolei Ren and colleagues](#) has estimated that training GPT-3 consumed around 5.4 million litres of water, and that a model like GPT-3 consumes roughly a 500 ml bottle of water for

every 10-50 responses. Global AI demand is projected to account for 4.2-6.6 billion cubic metres of water withdrawal by 2027 - exceeding half the total annual water withdrawal of the United Kingdom. [Some argue that these gross numbers are very misleading](#) - and that there have been demonstrably [false claims](#) over water effects on residents. There is no doubt that the [water usage of data centers](#) is highly variable. What is harder to dispute is that, particularly in areas which are already water-stressed and at a time when rising temperatures further threaten water reliability, the data center water issue has touched a very raw nerve.

Beyond these headline grievances, communities have a plethora of interconnected concerns: air pollution from unpermitted diesel backup generators; the loss of high quality soil, farmland and rural character; eye-popping tax abatements that let immensely profitable companies avoid contributing to the communities they burden; noise so severe that residents describe children sleeping in basements wearing headphones; secrecy via non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) with elected officials; surveillance and invasion of privacy via video cameras; [the concentration of facilities in Black and low-income neighbourhoods](#) already overburdened with pollution; grid reliability and blackout risk; and damage to historic sites and natural areas; and a cost benefit analysis that doesn't add up: ["\\$3 billion boxes that create maybe 30 jobs"](#).

Running through nearly all of these is a [deeper grievance about the democratic process](#) itself. This infrastructure is frequently [built in secrecy, with the widespread use of nondisclosure agreements and shell companies](#), meaning that the people most affected are excluded from decisions. Communities discover data center proposals overnight, with little notice and no meaningful consultation. The sense that decisions have already been made - that Big Tech and state government will build regardless of what local populations know or want - is a powerful radicalising force. In Montour County, Pennsylvania, where some farms have been in the same family for six or seven generations, a poultry hatchery worker co-founded a citizens' group that [drew 120 people to its first meeting and quickly gathered 3,000 petition signatures](#) - roughly twice the township's population.

Case study: New Jersey residents come together

Despite New Jersey being the densest state in the US, dozens of data center proposals have cropped up in every corner of the state, only to meet a groundswell of opposition from neighbors, youth groups, and local elected officials.

The Gen Z activist group [Climate Revolution Action Network](#) (CRAN) of New Jersey has been one group at the center of the fight. Their members have expressed grave concerns about projects shrouded in secrecy that could have substantial deleterious impacts on residential areas and the environment. In early 2026, youth volunteers with CRAN partnered with local residents to stop four AI data center projects and passed ordinances to slow them down in five municipalities across the state.

“Residents are angry because random people are coming into town and taking away their resources, especially water. People in South Jersey are worried about impacts on well water, all for a building none of us can use that will just be an eyesore,” Kayleigh Henry, Ecology Director for CRAN told us.

CRAN has gained hundreds of members interested in fighting data centers across the state, as well as getting considerable interest from neighboring states and elected officials in the NJ State House. A [viral video](#) of Executive Director Ben Dziobek yelling, “They cancelled it” outside a public meeting has been viewed over 6 million times.

** Image from Climate Revolution Action Network website.*

Of data centers that face sustained local opposition, [about 40 per cent are eventually cancelled or moved](#). By the second quarter of 2025, [opposition was double that of the previous year](#), with an estimated \$98 billion in projects blocked or delayed and 188 active opposition groups operating nationwide. The demands emerging from these campaigns range from the project-specific to the structural: moratoriums on new construction; mandatory environmental impact assessments; requirements that data centers pay the full cost of the grid infrastructure they need; water use caps and disclosure; enforcement of Clean Air Act standards; zoning protections for agricultural and residential land; and an end to the secrecy that has defined the industry's expansion. [Over 200 environmental organisations have called for a national moratorium](#).

Case study: Hancock County, Indiana - defending the orchard

On 8 May 2025, at a packed public meeting at Greenfield-Central High School, a proposed AI data center requiring [rezoning of over 700 acres](#) of agricultural land near Tuttle Orchards faced fierce community opposition. Residents raised concerns about impacts on agriculture, local ecosystems, and the rural character of the area. The orchards, a longstanding local business, opposed the project directly. Following the meeting, the developer Surge Development withdrew its rezoning application. This was not a typical environmentalist campaign - it was a rural, conservative community defending a way of life.

** Image from Greenfield reporter. File photo*

Worse than the electricity bill: AI as enabler of fossil fuel extraction

Gas-powered data centers could alone “[emit more greenhouse gases than entire nations](#)” and the physical infrastructure of AI is driving a whole new sector of emissions - but these direct harms are just the tip of an iceberg. An important and less-discussed dimension of the AI-climate nexus is not about the harms that data centers themselves cause - but about what the AI they are powering is being used for.

The fossil fuel industry is one of the most prolific and earliest adopters of AI. Companies including Shell, ExxonMobil, Chevron, Saudi Aramco and Petrobras are actively investing in AI across every stage of the oil and gas life cycle. Shell has announced it will use [generative AI to hasten exploration](#). An [IBM survey](#) found that 44 per cent of oil and gas drillers are already using AI in exploration, with another 45 per cent planning to do so within three years. Meanwhile, [just 14 per cent of producers use AI for emissions monitoring or leak detection](#).

The structural enablers are equally significant. Microsoft controls nearly [60 per cent of all cloud services contracts](#) with the oil and gas industry. Independent analyses have shown that just two of these contracts had a greater emissions impact than Microsoft's entire Scope 1-3 emissions. Google holds AI contracts with Total, Shell, Schlumberger and Chevron. NVIDIA is promoting "success stories" from Saudi Aramco, Shell and Petrobras.

[Global Witness](#) has argued that the emissions *enabled* by AI through fossil fuel extraction could dramatically exceed the footprint of the AI infrastructure itself. This framing - "enabled emissions" - deserves wider currency. It shifts the debate from a narrow focus on data center electricity to the much larger question of what the technology is being built to do. As [Bashir and colleagues at MIT](#) have argued, a narrow focus on energy efficiency can actually make AI's environmental challenges more pronounced, because improved efficiency drives greater total demand rather than reducing consumption - the [Jevons paradox](#) applied to compute.

But could data centers speed progress on clean energy?

The optimistic case for data centers focuses on their potential as drivers of clean energy and renewables. Big tech companies are among the world's largest corporate buyers of clean energy, having collectively contracted almost [50 GW of renewable capacity](#). There is a growing trend towards co-locating data centers alongside new renewable generation. The argument is that data centers, as capital-rich partners, could help finance grid upgrades that benefit everyone.

The counter-evidence, however, is substantial, and a key word is “could.” With a barren landscape of regulatory frameworks and freshly eliminated basic protections in the US (the data center capital of the world) there are no mandates driving renewable development alongside data center development. In the [Zero Trust AI Governance](#) released in 2023, the prominent think tank AI Now made a compelling case that the current incentive structure all but guarantees poor outcomes, and the current projects are already confirming this trajectory.

One problem is timing: data centers can be built in about three years, but grid infrastructure and renewable capacity take far longer - and the gap is being filled by fossil fuels. Goldman Sachs estimates that new electricity demand from data centers by 2030 will be met [60 per cent by gas and only 40 per cent by renewables](#). In the US, around 56 per cent of electricity currently powering data centers comes from [fossil fuels](#). According to [Global Energy Monitor](#), the US nearly tripled its gas-fired generating capacity in development in 2025, reaching almost 252 GW, with more than a third slated to directly power data centers on-site. In Ireland, 11 data centers are [already contracted to connect directly to the gas network](#), with a further 22 in the pipeline. Google’s data center build out is [going big on natural gas partnerships](#) and Elon Musk, going a step further, has won a permit for a [methane-powered center](#) in Mississippi. There is even the danger that the decline of coal power could be reversed, with [retired plants being pulled back online](#) to power data centers.

Case study: Okmulgee County, Oklahoma: sovereignty

The Muscogee Nation purchased land in Okmulgee County in 2021 with the promise of improving food security. When a data center rezoning plan materialised instead, Jordan Harmon, a Muscogee Nation citizen and policy specialist at the Indigenous Environmental Network, [connected the proposal](#) to broader patterns of dispossession: "They need these data centers for their programs like AI facial recognition to surveil and police people, including Indigenous people, who are also being detained by ICE. This is all a part of the legacy of colonialism and imperialism." The case adds an indigenous justice dimension to data center debates.

What about AI being used for good?

An honest account must reckon with the fact that, as well as enabling harm, data centers also power genuinely beneficial work. AI is accelerating climate modelling, drug discovery and renewable energy forecasting. [Google DeepMind's GNoME tool](#) has predicted 2.2 million new crystal structures - equivalent to roughly 800 years of conventional materials science - including 528 potential lithium-ion conductors that could improve next-generation batteries. An [MIT team has used machine learning](#) to identify new low-carbon alternatives for cement, a material responsible for around 8 per cent of global CO2 emissions. Most people would regard this work as valuable.

Public attitudes to AI are not straightforwardly hostile. According to the influential 2025 [Pew Research Center survey](#), 50% are 'more concerned than excited about the increased use of AI in daily life' (up from 37% in 2021), 10% are more excited than concerned and 38% are equally excited and concerned.

50% of Americans are more concerned than excited about the increased use of AI in daily life

% of U.S. adults who say the increased use of artificial intelligence (AI) in daily life makes them feel ...

Note: Respondents who did not give an answer are not shown.
Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted June 9-15, 2025.
"How Americans View AI and Its Impact on People and Society"

PEW RESEARCH CENTER

[Globally, a majority](#) still see AI products and services as more beneficial than harmful, and even in the US - where the public is more sceptical - [people are significantly more positive about AI in areas like medical research](#) than about its effects on jobs and the economy. But the direction of travel shows that concern is rising, not falling. And when [Quinnipiac asked Americans](#) whether AI development is being led by people who represent their interests, just 5 per cent said yes. [We are not getting the AI we were promised.](#)

Some of the most effective data center campaigns have not been framed as 'anti-AI' protests. They have been communities demanding democratic control over decisions that affect their water, energy, air and land. In our recent [Social Change Lab study](#) looking at which AI harms and risks would galvanise the public to contest AI, we found that the environmental costs of AI - the water, energy, and land consumed by data centers - was the issue that most increased their willingness to take action. Framing demands around governance - who decides what gets built, where, using what energy, for whose benefit - may have the potential to build a bigger tent than blanket opposition to data centers.

The bigger fight

The convergence of climate and AI accountability concerns is not accidental. Both movements are confronting similar underlying problems: profit-hungry corporate executives making decisions with sweeping consequences for society as they race for unfathomable profits amidst greatly diminished regulation and eroded democratic governance. The five companies building most of the world's data centers - Amazon, Microsoft, Google, Meta and Apple - are also among the most powerful corporations that have ever existed. Their combined lobbying spend, their capacity to write the rules they are then governed by, and the speed at which they can reshape communities, labour markets and energy systems are all without modern precedent. As [AI writer Brian Merchant has put it](#), the problem is not the technology itself (as reflected in the public's mixed feelings) but its political economy - "developed and sold by Silicon Valley oligopolies, for the benefit of tech billionaires, with the intent of surveilling, deskilling, and eroding labour."

Data centers are where this political economy becomes physical. These buildings act as eloquent symbols. They are the point at which the abstraction of "AI" (and the abstraction of "climate change") meets a real community's water supply, electricity grid and planning process. That is why the data center movement matters beyond the data centers themselves. It is one of the very few places where ordinary people can exercise democratic leverage over a technology, and the industries fueling it to the detriment of our planet, that is otherwise being imposed on them without their consent.

One key strength of the organic, cross-movement alliance fighting data center development is that residents have repeatedly put aside their differences to focus instead on where their goals converge. Key players including farmers, worried parents, AI accountability groups, climate campaigners and many more are coming together particularly around the shared concern about *who controls technology*. This concern transcends disagreements people might have about AI's merits, environmental politics and political party allegiance - and instead binds them by a shared apprehension about concentrated corporate power and the failure to regulate it.

What these diverse constituencies bring to a data center alliance is potentially powerfully complementary. The UK anti-fracking movement offers a useful precedent: it brought together an unlikely coalition of environmentalists, trade unions, farmers and rural landowners, and Conservative-voting homeowners in the Home Counties - united not by shared politics but by shared opposition. They were not opposing energy itself; they were

insisting that *this* energy, extracted *this* way, at *this* cost to *these* communities, was [not acceptable](#). A data center campaign can occupy similar ground - focused on democratic accountability and community consent rather than on AI itself - not “no AI” but “not *this* AI”.

The role of philanthropic strategy

While the data center fight is already taking off organically, philanthropy can help resource strategic, nuanced fights that build momentum beyond “not in my backyard” activism and growing toward a national or international coalition. [Climate Emergency Fund](#) acts as a bridge between grassroots movements and philanthropy; this positions us well to empower the fight against data centers, easily the cutting edge of climate organising right now. Already in 2026, more than a third of our fund’s granted support has gone to groups planning campaigns centered around data centers and AI. As the most significant institutional funder of disruptive climate activism, our decision to direct resources towards data center resistance also reflects a judgement that this is where grassroots energy, public concern, and campaign opportunity most clearly align with shared momentum.

It also underscores our organizational decision to double down on climate at a time when even climate activists are tempted to focus elsewhere. Many activists are turning away from centering “climate”. The [Sunrise Movement](#) has decided they must first fight against authoritarianism, and major philanthropic organizations like the [Gates Foundation](#) have signaled an interest in prioritising affordability and “kitchen sink” issues ahead of climate action.

Climate Emergency Fund views the data center fight as the nexus of these concerns. Rather than seeing the issue of rising authoritarianism or affordability as distinct, or as prerequisites to the climate fight, data center resistance allows the climate movement to highlight precisely where environmental harm for maximal profit and the erosion of democracy merge.

This decision also allows us to do what we do best – move early-stage funding to new groups, sometimes before they even have a name. To build the kind of momentum that sets the political agenda, we serve as venture philanthropy, providing strategic, fast-moving funding that follows emerging opportunities rather than waiting for established institutional channels. Both the anti-fracking movement in the US, as well as the ultimate passage of the Inflation Reduction Act, were catalysed in part by early philanthropic bets on local and national organising. Data center resistance may follow a similar pattern, with

philanthropic investment helping to build the connective tissue between isolated local fights and a coherent national and international movement.

A global movement in formation

The data center resistance to date has been most dramatic in the US, but it is not just an American story. In Ireland, where data centers already consume [22 per cent of national electricity](#) and use more power than every urban home in the country, Friends of the Earth has been running an "Energy for Who?" campaign demanding a national moratorium, and the utilities regulator has imposed an effective freeze on new data center grid connections in Dublin. In the Netherlands, local opposition - including farmers challenging environmental damage - [derailed Meta's mega-project in Zeewolde](#) and led parliament to pass a motion [effectively banning new hyperscale data centers](#) until the government formulated a national policy. In France, the March 2026 municipal elections saw data centers become an electoral issue, with candidates in [at least 10 towns campaigning against new facilities](#) or calling for moratoriums. In Chile, community resistance led by activist Pamela Ramirez [halted a Google data center in Santiago](#) over water concerns. In Uruguay, campaigners went to court to discover that a Google facility's cooling towers would need 7.6 million litres of potable water a day - their slogan was "No es sequía, es saqueo!" ("It's not drought, it's pillage!"). In the UK, [Global Action Plan coordinated days of action](#) in February 2026 against data center expansion, and a hyperscale facility near London now faces a [legal challenge on environmental impact grounds](#). The pattern is the same everywhere: communities discover what is being built, often in secret; they organise around water, energy, land and democratic process; and they often win.

Data centers represent something the climate movement has not had in some time: a live, rapidly evolving campaign moment with genuine potential for broad public engagement. Unlike decarbonisation targets, which can feel abstract and long-term, data center resistance is concrete, local and immediate. The entry points for civic participation are real and accessible - planning and permitting battles offer concrete roles for people who would never attend a climate march but will turn up to a town board meeting about their water supply or electricity bill.

The data center build out has become a symbol for wider community grievances about who is shaping our future, uniting diverse concerns and proposals about democratic planning, community consent, energy and water standards, grid impact assessments, moratoriums in water-stressed or grid-constrained areas. These are demands that can

unite people who agree on very little else. And they connect the local fight against a specific data center to much larger questions - about who controls the most powerful technology of our time, in whose interest it operates, and whether the public gets any say at all.

AI capabilities and energy demands are evolving so fast that specific claims made today may date quickly. The durable argument is not about any particular energy figure or water consumption estimate. It is about a principle: that the public should have a meaningful say in decisions that reshape their communities, their energy systems, and their relationship to the natural world.

[Social Change Lab](#) is a nonprofit that conducts research on protest and people-powered movements. The [Climate Emergency Fund](#) is the largest funder of the climate movement. The [Center on Nonviolent Conflict Research](#) is an independent educational foundation that supports the study and strategic application of nonviolent action worldwide.

This is the third in a series of discussion papers from [Social Change Lab](#) on the future avenues for the climate movement. The first examined how [extreme weather events](#) create windows for political change. The second, discussed [the potential of strategic adaptation](#).